

Influence of Improvisation Education to Teamwork Abilities Based on Competency

Shogo Takezaki¹, Megumi Yamashita¹, Hiroshi Hasegawa¹

¹ Shibaura Institute of Technology, Graduate School of Engineering and Science (JAPAN)

Email: mf20049@shibaura-it.ac.jp, mf19078@shibaura-it.ac.jp, h-hase@shibaura-it.ac.jp

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5095630>

Abstract

With the complexity of society, it is changing into where sudden and irregular problems are becoming more frequent. In the society based on this uncertainty, it is important to demonstrate teamwork that can be flexible and appropriate to respond to unexpected problems. Furthermore, the society is becoming diverse nowadays, and teams frequently include members from many different countries, fields, and cultures. To carry out projects in this society, it is necessary to understand the characteristics and preferences of the individuals who belong to the team to perform well under unexpected circumstances. This paper focused on the change in performance of each participant before and after Oh My God Experience (OMG), which is an improvisation education throughout the Cross-cultural Engineering Project (CEP) based on global Project-Based Learning (gPBL). Each participant of the CEP at SIT in 2019 and KMUTT in 2020 answered a questionnaire on how the individual ability (Team-oriented, Backup, Monitoring and Leadership) affects the performance in the team. Furthermore, the competency of the participants was measured by Progress Report On Generic skills (PROG) after the CEP. The results of the questionnaire were compared with the results of the PROG to analyze the correlation between them. The result showed that participants who answered that the team-oriented skills were important or difficult before and after the OMG scored higher on the PROG with a significant difference in "Attunement" and "Harmony" than those who answered that they were not. This suggests that they found them difficult during the OMG because they were aware of them, and that they are in the stage of conscious maturation. Alternatively, the participants who answered that it was important or difficult before and after the OMG scored lower on the PROG with a significant difference in "Autonomy" than those who answered otherwise. This may be because they are in the stage of unconscious maturation and are not aware that they are important or difficult.

Keywords: Teamwork Competency, Improvisation Education, Project-based Learning, Multinational Team

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

In recent years, unpredictable problems and rapid changes are frequently occurring in society due to digitalization, globalization, and diversification. This environment is called VUCA, a term coined from Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and Ambiguity. In this VUCA society, unanticipated problems frequently arise in the course of work (Petrie Nick, 2011). Therefore, leaders need to be cooperative with their teams and have good communication (Lawrence, 2013). In projects, it is important for teams to be flexible to change and recognize opportunities to improve their deliverables to produce the best results under time and cost constraints. Under these constraints, teamwork becomes critical. It is difficult to achieve high performance as a team if the team only focuses on individual tasks, but if the team is aware of teamwork, the team can achieve high performance, leading to better deliverables (Aikawa, 2012) to strengthen the individual teamwork skills of team members, educational institutions need to provide educational methods using active learning. In recent years, universities have been using Problem-Based Learning (PBL), an educational method that provides students with an environment to work in teams to solve problems that exist in modern society. PBL is an educational method that provides students with the benefits of collaboration, from which they learn the importance of teamwork. In this paper, PBL is defined as a project in which a team of international members from multiple nationalities and cultures works together to solve a problem.

1.2 Expectation from conducting improvisation education

One of the active learning methods, called improvised education, has been gaining attention in recent years. This strengthens the ability to solve problems, be creative, and build relationships among members through group work. Improvisation has long been practiced in the fields of music and theater, but in recent years, it has been incorporated into education as an active learning program in many academic fields, as its improvisation and creativity are also required in business situations. In recent years, however, improvisation and creativity have been incorporated into education as active learning programs in many universities, as they are required in business situations as well (Alves & Leão, 2015; Guerra et al., 2017; Jollands et al., 2012). For example, students improvise and dance to background music that changes one after another, such as hip-hop and African drumming, or simulate peacekeeping in Bosnia over a three-day period. The effects of this improvisational education include a more positive attitude toward sudden changes, improved teamwork, quicker decision making, and smoother project management. At Shibaura Institute of Technology, we are conducting a Cross-cultural Engineering Project based on PBL (Kongwat et al., 2020; Navas, 2017, 2018). In this context, we are implementing an improvisational education called OMG (Oh My God). Figure 1 shows the events and specific implementation schedule during the CEP.

Figure1. Activity schedule in the CEP

1.3 Research question and objective

There has been a lot of research done on teamwork. For example, research is being conducted in the field of management to understand what makes a good team, what improves team performance, and how to effectively recognize team situations (Salas & Fiore, 2004). In addition, today, much attention is being paid to competencies, which were introduced by McClelland of Harvard University in the 1970s and are behavioral traits common to high achievers. In today's world, where unexpected problems occur frequently, competency is an important element in team projects and is one of the factors that improve team performance (Yamashita & Hasegawa, 2020). However, there is a lack of research on the impact of individual competencies on team performance under unforeseen circumstances, especially on the impact of improvisation education on individual behavioral characteristics. As the research question, "How does the improvisation education affect individual teamwork competencies?" has been picked up. This paper examines how individual teamwork competencies (team orientation, back-up, teamwork, and leadership skills) affect team performance under unforeseen circumstances and investigates the impact of improvisation education on individual competencies.

2 Methodology

2.1 Ability changing experiment

2.1.1 Content of the Pre-Post OMG questionnaire

A questionnaire was administered before and after the OMG to investigate changes in individual teamwork abilities before and after the OMG. The questions were developed based on the results of Dickson & McIntyre's study (Dickson & McIntyre, 1997), referring to the teamwork skills defined by Aikawa et al (Aikawa, 2012). as consisting of team thinking skills, backup skills, monitoring skills, and leadership skills.

Table 1. Content of the Pre-OMG questionnaire

Questions	
1. What do you think it is the most important factor to work in a group under unexpected situation such as OMG experience? (Single or Multiple answer are allowable)	
Team-oriented	Keep pace with members/Make sure there are no disagreements Keep the group balance/Consider and accept different values Clearly assert your opinion
Backup	Encourage when members are negative Give an advice to the members/Provide acquired information Support members whose work hasn't finished
Monitoring	Check and confirm the progress of the member's work Listen to the member's opinion and reflect to yours Compare the opinion of yours and the members throughout the discussion
Leadership	Provide your knowledge willingly Create a positive atmosphere for the team Get along with your team members equally Find the best solution to failure and take action Others
2. How do you feel or want to be after your group have accomplished the OMG experience? (Free description)	

Table 2. Content of the Post-OMG questionnaire

Questions	
1. Which of these elements were difficult throughout OMG experience? (Single or Multiple answer are allowable)	
Team-oriented	Keep pace with members/Make sure there are no disagreements Keep the group balance/Consider and accept different values Clearly assert your opinion
Backup	Encourage when members are negative Give an advice to the members/Provide acquired information Support members whose work hasn't finished
Monitoring	Check and confirm the progress of the member's work Listen to the member's opinion and reflect to yours Compare the opinion of yours and the members throughout the discussion
Leadership	Provide your knowledge willingly Create a positive atmosphere for the team Get along with your team members equally Find the best solution to failure and take action Others
2. Please write down at least one improvement or suggestion for your better team performance based on OMG experience. (Free description)	

2.1.2 Subject and Conditions

The survey was held at SIT Omiya December 2019 and KMUTT in February 2020. For CEP2019@Omiya and CEP2020@KMUTT, it was conducted to participants majoring science and engineering (Table 4). Each Pre-OMG questionnaire was conducted on day4, and on day6 for Post-OMG questionnaire.

Table 3. Breakdown of the respondents for CEP2019@Omiya and CEP2020@KMUTT

CEP2019@Omiya			CEP2020@KMUTT		
Nationality	Respondent		Nationality	Respondent	
	Pre-OMG	Post-OMG		Pre-OMG	Post-OMG
Japan	32 (42%)	27 (38%)	Japan	19 (58%)	15 (63%)
Malaysia	3 (4%)	3 (4%)	Thailand	13 (39%)	7 (29%)
China	5 (7%)	5 (7%)	Indonesia	1 (3%)	1 (4%)
Thailand	14 (18%)	17 (24%)	Laos	0 (0%)	1 (4%)
Vietnam	5 (7%)	5 (7%)	Total	33 (100%)	24 (100%)
India	3 (4%)	2 (3%)			
Indonesia	3 (4%)	3 (4%)			
Brazil	3 (4%)	3 (4%)			
Netherlands	1 (1%)	1 (1%)			
Poland	2 (3%)	2 (3%)			
Brunei	1 (1%)	1 (1%)			
Mongolia	2 (3%)	1 (1%)			
Cambodia	1 (1%)	1 (1%)			
Australia	1 (1%)	1 (1%)			
Singapore	0 (0%)	1 (1%)			
Taiwan	0 (0%)	1 (1%)			
Total	76 (100%)	74 (100%)			

2.2 PROG test

In order to measure the competency skills of the students, we administered the PROG test (Progress Report On Generic skills). This PROG test is provided by KAWAIJUKU and RIASEC. They created a database of the behavioral characteristics of young leaders active in the real world and extracted response patterns from it. After that, a scoring logic is constructed, and in addition to self-evaluation, an objective evaluation index is provided to enable a composite evaluation of generic skills. This PROG test was given to the students after the completion of CEP.

2.3 Linking team-oriented ability with result of PROG test

By linking the results of the questionnaire in section 2.1.1 with the results of the PROG test, we investigated the impact of OMG on individual teamwork skills. In the pre-OMG questionnaire, those who answered that the element was important were grouped into Pre-group1, and those who did not answer that the element was important were grouped into Pre-group2. Similarly, for the Post-OMG questionnaire, those who answered that the element was difficult were designated as Post-group 1, and those who did not answer that the element was difficult were designated as Post-group 2. Next, the results of the questionnaire and the PROG test were linked. Figure 2 below shows the team-oriented competencies in the questionnaire results and the corresponding competency components of the PROG test. the PROG test scores of the students in each group were extracted, and then the scores for each element were averaged. Then, a significance test was conducted on the differences in the mean scores of each group.

Figure 2. Corresponding table

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Team-oriented ability changes due to OMG

The results of the questionnaires conducted for Pre-OMG and Post-OMG are shown below. Figure 3 shows the results of the CEP2019@Omiya questionnaire, and Figure 4 shows the results of the CEP2020@KMUTT questionnaire. The numbers in the figures correspond to the numbers in Figure 5. From Figure 3 and 4, we can see that the team-oriented ability increased in Post from Pre. This can be attributed to the fact that students have come to place more importance on team-oriented skills through OMG.

Figure 3. Changes in four types of abilities between Pre and Post OMG for CEP2019@Omiya

Figure 4. Changes in four types of abilities between Pre and Post OMG for CEP2020@KMUTT

1. Keep pace with members/Make sure there are no disagreements
2. Keep the group balance/Consider and accept different values
3. Clearly assert your opinion
4. Encourage when members are negative
5. Give an advice to the members/Provide acquired information
6. Support members whose work hasn't finished
7. Check and confirm the progress of the member's work
8. Listen to the member's opinion and reflect to yours
9. Compare the opinion of yours and the members throughout the discussion
10. Provide your knowledge willingly
11. Create a positive atmosphere for the team
12. Get along with your team members equally
13. Find the best solution to failure and take action

Figure 5. Choices for the questionnaire

3.2 Correlation between team-oriented ability and result of PROG test

From section 2.3, we present the results of the significant difference test for the differences in the mean scores of each group. First, Figure 6 shows the mean scores of the OMGs conducted at CEP2019@Omiya that showed significant differences. Note that in Figures 6 to 9, the * mark means that there was a significant difference ($p < .05$), and the † mark means that there was a significant trend ($p < .10$).

Figure 6. Harmony for CEP2019@Omiya

Next, the significant differences in the mean scores of the OMGs performed in CEP2020@KMUTT are shown in Figures 7 through 9.

Figure 7. Tuning for CEP2020@KMUTT

Figure 8. Harmony for CEP2020@KMUTT

Figure 9. Independence for CEP2020@KMUTT

From this analysis of the questionnaire for the OMG experience at CEP2019@Omiya, Figures 6 through 8 show that the mean score for Group 1 was higher than that for Group 2 with a significant difference or a significant trend. This means that in the pre-semester, those who originally had a high level of ability placed importance on this ability, while in the post-semester, the mean score of those who found this element difficult was higher than that of those who did not, suggesting that they were aware of this element during the OMG experience

and found it difficult. It seems that they are at the stage of conscious maturity. On the other hand, Figure 9 shows that the average score of Group 2 was higher than that of Group 1 in both Pre and Post. This may be since they are in the stage of unconscious maturity and are not aware of the importance or difficulty of the task in the first place.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, the impact of OMG on individual teamwork ability was discussed by relating it to individual competencies. The results confirmed that team-oriented ability is an important factor for teamwork in OMG. Therefore, we believe that improvisation education changes individual teamwork competencies. As a future prospect, we will continue to conduct questionnaires and surveys in the same way to investigate the impact on individual teamwork ability. We will also improve the OMG based on the results revealed in this study to improve the behavioural characteristics necessary to produce higher quality deliverables.

5 References

- Petrie, Nick. (2011). Future Trends in Leadership Development. Center for Creative Leadership.
- Lawrence, Kirk. (2013). Developing leaders in a VUCA environment
- Aikawa, A., Takamoto, M., Sugimori, S., Furuya, A. (2012). Development and validity check of a scale measuring individual teamwork competency in a group.
- Salas, E., Ed. & Fiore S., M. (2004), Team cognition: Understanding the factors that drive process and performance.
- Yamashita, M., Hasegawa, H. (2020). Efficiency of Individual Competency in Teamwork Under Unexpected Situation in Project-Based Learning
- Dickson T. L. & McIntyre, R. M. (1997). A conceptual framework for teamwork measurement.
- Kongwat, S., Watanabe, D., Mochizuki, K., Koike, R., Navas, H., & Hasegawa, H. (2020). Finding Attractive Solutions based on Idea Creation Support System for Cross-cultural Engineering Project.
- Navas, H. (2017). "Global PBL" na FCT NOVA - "through the problem solving experience."
- Navas, H. (2018). Global PBL 2018 na FCT NOVA.
- Alves, Anabela C., & Leão, C. P. (2015). Action, Practice and Research in Project Based Learning in an Industrial Engineering and Management Program.
- Guerra, A., Ulseth, R., & Kolmos, A. (2017). *PBL in Engineering Education* (A. Guerra, R. Ulseth, & A. Kolmos (eds.)). SensePublishers. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6300-905-8>
- Jollands, M., Jolly, L., & Molyneaux, T. (2012). Project-based learning as a contributing factor to graduates' work readiness. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2012.665848>